

HOW DO PEOPLE IN UZBEKISTAN USE AI IN THEIR JOBS AND STUDIES? DOES
AI SERVE USEFUL PURPOSES OR MAKE INDIVIDUALS LAZY?

Sardorbek Qo‘ziboyev To‘lqinovich

Computer science student from Jizzakh, Uzbekistan

Abstract : This research paper explores the integration of Artificial Intelligence in education and workplaces in Uzbekistan, striving to understand the public perspective and usage trends. The study evaluates the perceived usefulness of AI and its reliance on it through interviews with 10 students from diverse academic fields and 10 professionals from different sectors in Uzbekistan. Overall, the study highlights the higher AI adaptation among computer science and IT-related workers, both in terms of unitality and daily usage, whereas participants from social sectors and students from biology and math classes turned out to be more cautious about using AI. In fact, every interviewed person showed no opposition to the development of AI, although their usage rates differ dramatically. When I compared my research with previous studies, I noticed that I gained similar results generally. However, as my study is the latest assessment with the painstaking methods, my conclusion presented clearer suggestions, emphasizing the need to educate individuals to ensure responsible usage among the broader population. The study generalizes the current, localized attitude toward AI integration in Uzbekistan and can serve as an informative tool for future research in this field.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, automation, AI tools, smart technology, digital transformation, AI in Uzbekistan, uzbek education system, job market in Uzbekistan, technology in Central Asia

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence has transformed various fields worldwide, particularly education, the workplace, and daily life. Since 2024, 14th October, when the President of Uzbekistan (Shavkat Mirziyoyev) approved the resolution to accelerate the development of AI technologies, Uzbek people have been using chatbots and other task-performer AI seriously more than any other apps or websites. The government wants to enter the top 50 countries on the AI Readiness Index and boost AI-driven software products and services to reach a market value of \$1.5 billion by 2030. However, the current implication of AI among Uzbek people raises some concerns about the future of AI-based technologies as most people are avoiding their daily tasks by merely assigning them to AI. Since the rise of AI, every single educational

center and many workplaces have generated AI tools, especially ChatGPT, to various degrees: Students are becoming lazy and giving their tasks to AI or sometimes leveraging AI to pass exams, forcing teachers to make rules regarding the usage of chatbots. Therefore, most Uzbek people still regard AI-based technologies as tools to cheat and as servants that encourage people to lead a sedentary lifestyle. Why don't people in my nation use AI as a source of information to learn?

This paper will first explore the background and literature on AI usage. Then, it will analyze how AI is affecting jobs and education in Uzbekistan - researching whether AI truly leads to productivity or presents an obstacle to independent thinking. A nuanced discussion of the findings will be provided in context, accompanied by an exploration of the theoretical and practical implications related to the usage of AI in education and offices. Finally, the paper will conclude by acknowledging the limitations of this research and outlining avenues for future work.

Literature Review

To understand the perception of AI among Uzbek people, it is important to scrutinize the existing research in the world regarding AI usage, examining the key themes in the integration of AI in education and offices and compare the worldwide trends to clarify the effects.

KEY THEMES REGARDING THE OBJECTIVES OF PEOPLE WHO USE AI AI adoption in Uzbekistan.

Uzbekistan's national strategy plans to promote the development of AI-based technologies and replace labor with effective digital machines. The policies and investment programs are working on accelerating the adoption of AI in every single sphere, spreading artificial intelligence applications across the country. The first step is creating the necessary infrastructure for the development of artificial intelligence technologies (Khakimov). To do so in Uzbekistan, politicians and IT specialists know that the expansion of broadband internet, the establishment of data centers, and the development of high-capacity computing systems for AI applications are at the forefront. A significant budget needs to be allocated for AI algorithms to work properly. Taking material aspects into account, the government is making serious investments in this direction (Uzdaily). There are several sectors(education, medicine, and agriculture) that must be placed above others when it comes to introducing AI-based technologies. Particularly in city areas, AI is proven to be useful for transport, energy management, and public services (GlobalCIO). As I mentioned earlier in the introduction,

Uzbekistan is seriously obsessed with turning every single sector in the government into AI-oriented workplaces by 2030, thereby reducing bureaucratic processes, increasing transparency and preventing corruption. (The Government Portal of the Republic Uzbekistan, 2024)

The role of AI in education

Since the first time we witnessed AI-oriented technologies in education, these algorithms have been transforming the way we typically teach and learn, making it personalized, engaging, and efficient (Alneyadi, Wardat, Alshannag, & Abu-Al-Aish, 2023). Artificial intelligence serves as a useful tool for machine learning and natural language processing to enhance the learning experience. (Alneyadi et al., 2023). Algorithms that enable analyzing the data, identifying patterns, and making predictions benefit educators in personalizing learning for each student (Khan et al., 2022). When we initially launched leveraging chatbots at schools and universities, most people embraced the revolution and regarded the chatbots, particularly ChatGPT, as an effective tool to accelerate the learning process without negatively affecting the quality of education overall (Al-Bahrani, 2022). However, what AI later turned out to be for some students is a servant who does tasks and exams without challenging the students' minds. Those students who don't use AI in the right way may be victims of the technology revolution, becoming lazy and academically weak (Zarei et al., 2022). Likewise, AI can have serious repercussions on teachers' passion and desire to teach if teachers exploit artificial intelligence to deal with their heavy workload. We cannot just announce the introduction of AI-based technologies in education without giving instructions to teachers about properly using them: not primarily to make teaching easier but to make it more effective (Samad, Hamza, Muazzam, Ahmer, et al., 2022). Overall, it is apparent that although artificial intelligence is useful and handy, its usage in education places some responsibility on the shoulders of both teachers and students. **AI can do in the workplace**

Fluctuations in social and organizational practices, changes in worker demographics, and advances in technology are rapidly reshaping the future of office work in ways that may amplify these potential detriments to worker health and well-being (Tamers, S.L. et al.). After COVID-19, organizations are considering changing from open environments with shared workstations, like hot-desking, to alternative workflows and work arrangements (Parker, L.D. et al., Green, N.; Tappin, D.; Bentley, T.). Now, managers get to use artificial intelligence to provide convenient and large-scale, yet individualized, interventions to handle different environmental interruptions and make a healthy, supportive workplace where workers can collaborate online or offline. When we think about automation in service-oriented industries,

the first thing that comes to mind is the replacement of human labor with machines (Wisskirchen, G.; Biacabe, B.T.; Bormann, U.; Muntz, A.; Niehaus, G.; Soler, G.J.; Von Brauchitsch, B.). However, some automation is created to make human workers stay and support their physical and emotional well-being to increase their productivity (Manuvinakurike, R. et al). Still, many of these systems disturb workers from their tasks to provide information or communicate with the system (Traum, D. et al.). Therefore, Scientists have another important duty: making AI-based machines that can monitor human workers' health and productivity without disturbing their work. Unfortunately, there are possibilities that some organizations may not incorporate AI-oriented machines even after many improvements due to fear of AI (Ernst, E et al.) and privacy concerns (Buchanan, B.G). We have already proven that we can integrate an AI system that can learn individual needs, enhance the work environment, and adapt to the changing behavior within the office workplace. A previously published holistic review of current evidence and gaps in knowledge relative to developing an AI system made it clear that we have to take office employees' perspectives, needs, and preferences into account (Aryal, A. et al). Artificial intelligence superior skills are mentioned many times as the main innovative factors that will transform the workplace and boost efficiency. However, if we fail to create a logical and matching bond between a human worker and an AI-based machine, we can have the opposite effect over time, with AI taking a heavy toll on future employment.

Benefits of AI-based technologies

When we talk about AI, several benefits pop up in our minds. Both in education and the workplace, artificial intelligence generally improves the skills of individuals and makes learning and growing easier through valuable materials and techniques. For example, in 2023, UNICEF collaborated with the Ministry of Preschool and School Education of Uzbekistan to pilot Edition, an AI-powered digital math learning platform. Over the course of 12 weeks, the platform was proven to be fruitful, as 527 random students from Tashkent city and region outperformed their peers, with an average improvement of 16.9 in mathematics skills. (UNICEF) It was practical evidence showing how useful and convenient AI-based teaching can be. Even teachers noted that Eduten's adaptive learning path and gamified tasks improved student engagement and motivation to study. It is merely one of the initiatives the Uzbek people showed to upgrade education; there are more AI-based projects introduced in the last five years, with most of them presenting positive outcomes. Likewise, similar useful projects are launched in business and many other important sectors of the government. Some of the research conducted by the Uzbek scholar Yormat Ilmidin Toshmatovich highlights the AI integration in

Uzbekistan's textile enterprises. (International Journal of Studies in Business Management, Economics and Strategies). The scholar emphasizes benefits such as process optimization, enhanced human resources management, improved data analytics, and informed decision-making. I firmly believe that these advancements lead to higher productivity and competitiveness within the textile sector.

Some drawbacks and stereotypes about AI usage.

In education and the workplace, AI may present several notable challenges. Although most scientists emphasize the benefits of AI in problem-solving and accuracy, normal users always possess the fear of AI controlling itself. There is an urban myth that AI can one day overtake the world, as in sci-fi movies, if technologies continue to develop at the current pace. However, those scholar who integrated the machines were always ahead of their inventions. In education, there is another problem with the mindset of certain teachers as they fear AI may replace their roles, making thousands of teachers jobless. These negative thoughts about the prospect of AI among teachers deter technologies from being openly welcomed by teachers and principals. In reality, AI is created as an assistant for teachers and can never replace human educators as technologies lack emotional knowledge. (Walden University, Using AI in learning). Nevertheless, there is an actual issue that needs to be solved to make AI impeccable. There are still some cases where AI-generated information turns out to be biased. The algorithm may serve detrimental purposes if one wants to use AI for his or her own advantage. AI cannot identify whether an action is moral or not, so if the ruler of AI doesn't want to use its machine for good purposes, AI cannot reject bad orders. In offices, employers have serious responsibilities since they monitor the flow of money. Biased AI technologies can even lead to bankruptcy or unfair lawsuits for the victims of the algorithm. (Walden University, Using AI in learning)

Methodology

When AI was introduced to my country, the first target of innovation was the main sector of the country that is education. There has been some research by professors and researchers, eventually presenting shallow or incomprehensive outcomes (Alneyadi, Wardat, Alshannag, & Abu-Al-Aish 2023). Unlikely, In my interview, I decided to include students from different fields of education like Math, IT, and Biology (3 out of 10 students were from math classes. 4 out of 10 students were from computer classes and the last 3 students were from biology classes.). Furthermore, I also take the genders of students into account and to make my research holistic, I included 5 males and 5 females. At school, I talked with each student at least

5-10 minutes individually. After communicating with each student and setting a friendly atmosphere during the chat, I asked two main questions:

1. "Has AI improved your learning experience?"
2. "Do you rely on AI to complete tasks you used to do manually?"

Then, I asked them to rate their answer on a scale of 1 to five (Likert scale) according to their positivity in their responses since their way of answering differs dramatically, creating problems when generalizing their responses.

Interview for workers

I researched the papers to learn the effect of AI on workplaces in Uzbekistan. However, I witnessed similar shortcomings in these studies; researchers have mostly failed to make comprehensive decisions by including every single important aspect throughout the research paper (Manuvinakurike et al. 2021). I started the research by searching for volunteers, who want to express their views regarding AI, from different fields and positions. I talked with the manager of the Youth Agency in Jizzakh and asked for help with finding suitable volunteers. They didn't reject me and provided certain rooms from their building for interviews and arranged special meetings with every single volunteer. Youth Agency found 10 employees from varying sectors and positions: software engineer and data analyst from computer science; IT support from Information Tech; doctor and nurse from medicine; teacher from education; HR manager and marketing specialist from Business; bank teller from Finance; and lawyer from Law.

In the conversations with workers, I initially created a friend zone like I had done with students in my previous interviews. Then I asked two main questions:

1. "Has AI made your job easier or harder?"
2. "Do you rely on AI to complete tasks you used to do manually?"

Then, I asked them to rate their answer on a scale of 1 to five (Likert scale) according to their positivity in their responses since their way of answering differs dramatically, creating problems when generalizing their responses.

Results/Findings Looking from an overall perspective, Computer students showed the highest rate of AI usage in their learning process, seriously relying on AI for most tasks while math and biology students represented relatively lower reliance on AI-based technologies during learning. On the whole, the effect of AI on students' productivity remarkably differed, as evident from the responses to the second question: Computer students approved the positive

impact of AI in education with average scores, whereas math and biology students didn't really regard AI as a vital tool for study.

In terms of details for the rates given by students showing how useful AI is for their study, computer students give the highest rate (4.5 out of 5), considerably greater than math and biology students, who are both at 3/5.

Their daily usage of AI showed a similar ranking. Math students confirmed they utilize AI for half of their tasks, with 2.5/5, compared to computer students (higher than math students) at 3/5 and biology students (lower than math students) at 2/5.

The results from my survey align with Alneyadi, Wardat, Alshannag, & Abu-Al-Aish (2023) in highlighting the varying levels of AI adoption among students from different academic disciplines. Their research emphasizes that AI enhances personalized learning experiences, particularly in fields that require computational problem-solving, such as computer science and engineering. This finding is consistent with my results, where computer science students demonstrated the highest reliance on AI for academic tasks.

However, my research presents a slight deviation in terms of how students from non-technical backgrounds perceive AI. While Alneyadi et al. (2023) suggest that AI-based learning tools can significantly improve engagement and efficiency across all subjects, my findings

indicate that math and biology students exhibit a more cautious approach, with a lower dependence on AI in their daily studies. This discrepancy could be attributed to differences in AI tool accessibility, teaching methods, or even student attitudes toward AI's role in analytical and experimental disciplines.

Another similarity is the concern over AI dependency. Alneyadi et al. (2023) discuss the potential risk of students over-relying on AI to complete assignments rather than developing critical thinking skills independently. My survey results support this concern, as even students who acknowledged AI's usefulness admitted to using it frequently for tasks they previously performed manually.

Interview results for workers

The table compares the rates regarding the usefulness and reliance on AI given by employees from different sectors of Uzbekistan.

Overall, the relatively higher ratings were represented by individuals who work with computers and doctors, while teachers, businessmen, and lawyers claimed to utilize AI considerably less and AI-based technologies don't play a very important role in their workplace.

Looking at the details for computer scientists, a software engineer, and a data analyst rated the usefulness of AI 4.5 and 4 out of 5, respectively, but the numbers switched when it comes to the reliance rates (software engineer at 4 and data analyst at 4.5). IT support from information Tech was slightly less than computer scientists, giving 3.5 for usage and 3 for reliance.

Regarding the details for those who rated lower, the nurse and marketing specialist judged the same for both categories (2.5 as the first answer and 2 as the second answer). Similarly, the teacher, HR manager, and bank teller gave the same respective scores of 2 and

1.5 as the first and second answers.

Job Position	Faculty	Has AI Made Job Easier? (1-5)	Do You Rely on AI for Manual Tasks? (1-5)
Software Engineer	Computer Science	4.5	4.0
Data Analyst	Computer Science	4.0	4.5
IT Support	Information Tech	3.5	3.0
Doctor	Medicine	3.0	2.5
Nurse	Medicine	2.5	2.0
Teacher	Education	2.0	1.5
HR Manager	Business Admin	2.0	1.5
Marketing Specialist	Business & Marketing	2.5	2.0
Bank Teller	Finance	2.0	1.5
Lawyer	Law	1.5	1.2

My research results obtained from interviews validate numerous aspects of Manuyinakurike et al. (2021) study. The research demonstrates how professionals working within technological sectors show a willingness to adopt AI because they understand it raises operational efficiency and decreases monotonous work requirements. The research results match my findings which show that software engineers and data analysts together with IT support technicians gave high ratings to both AI usefulness and dependence across professions. Significant differences appear during evaluations between technical and non-technical occupational sectors. An increasing number of administrators and social workers display a growing appreciation for AI technologies according to Manuyinakurike et al. but my research indicates staff at various positions including teaching, lawmaking, human resources operations, and banking remain unconvinced about AI's worth. At present, most Uzbek professionals view AI technology as irrelevant or encroaching on their work or AI applications remain in their infancy in non-technical fields.

Both studies focus on the industry AI adoption speed, but my research adds regional relevance by examining the specific Uzbek technology conditions through professional training and acceptance patterns.

Discussion

I have examined the impact of AI and individuals' attitudes towards digitalization in almost all the important sectors, with education being specifically scrutinized through

interviews. There are some patterns in the answers for certain types of fields. For example, those spheres, that are related to IT or computers, are seriously more affected by AI, whereas social jobs seem to use less often and don't believe in AI when deciding on job-related decisions. These trends prove that AI-based algorithms haven't succeeded in performing the tasks that need human factors to be done. When interviews were conducted, I realized that he takes his job seriously and he firmly believes that AI puts individuals' privacy and social rights in danger. Lawyers' job demands different solutions to different situations; AI is unable to handle these problems as its algorithm uses only previous information to present solutions. On the other hand, computer scientists and those who are studying this subject reacted similarly to my answers. They have already connected their job with AI and regard it as an extremely useful tool for job stability and consistent improvement.

Answer for the 1st question

As artificial intelligence fails to work creatively, it was clear from interviews that people don't believe in AI when it comes to dealing with tasks that demand a new attitude; At least, even computer students, check the source and accuracy of outcomes AI presents

in such cases. Although people admit artificial intelligence's incredibility, they still suggest AI has made their job easier and accelerated students' learning process. One computer science student Asilbek especially said, "AI's useful aspects can easily outweigh its rare mistakes, and I have never faced any serious results when AI made some mistakes. Scholars just want to warn people about the possibilities, but they also know AI hasn't led to detrimental consequences yet". Interviewed people's positivity about AI usage implicitly demonstrates their general approval for AI-based technologies. Even lawyers and biology students, who leverage considerably less than other professions and students, didn't deny the positive impact of AI on their jobs. Furthermore, apart from study and work, individuals use ChatGPT to ask a piece of advice on any random issue at home and confirm the convenience of the algorithm. They want AI to stay in their lives and leverage it on a daily basis, albeit at different levels.

Answer for the 2nd question

According largely to the nature of their field and familiarity with technology, overall data from both students and employees shows apparent trends in AI reliance. One connection that is clear across both groups is that individuals engaged in computer-related disciplines (whether students or professionals) highlight a higher reliance on AI compared to those in other areas.

Computer science majors rated their reliance on AI significantly higher than math and biology students, which reflects their routine engagement with coding tools, AI-assisted research, and automation platforms. My findings from the question largely align with those of Alneyadi et al (2023) who contended that students in tech-driven fields benefit more directly from AI technologies in education. Similarly, computer professionals rated their reliance higher, further confirming that regular interaction with AI systems fosters a stronger dependence on algorithms. On the other hand, those employees from non-technical roles like teacher, HR manager, and marketing rated reliance significantly lower. These proven fields requiring human interaction, judgment or soft skills may be slower to adopt AI. What is more, I learned that AI adaptation is not uniform across sectors, but instead heavily depends on how well artificial intelligence tools handle different tasks.

Conclusion

Throughout the research process, I witnessed interviewed people generally off a positive opinion about AI regardless of their reliance. None of the participants expressed direct opposition to the development of AI-based technologies in the education and workplace. In many sectors, AI is assisting individuals to handle some time-consuming tasks more quickly and acquire rare knowledge with the power of algorithms. Both students and employees know how to properly use AI and they avoid the exploitation of AI for negative purposes. I, therefore, concluded that we can believe in educated people, but those who are uneducated and less

informed about the rules of using AI may misuse artificial intelligence and cause a so-called disaster that has been overstated by the media.

I did my best to avoid previous shortcomings in my research. I took gender, role, age, and the professions of people into account when inferring an overall conclusion. I am pretty sure that future experiments and researchers can use my research paper for their studies and consider my data very objective and real as I paid attention to even tiny aspects and scrutinized previous relevant research papers and included their important details in my own paper.

In the future research, scholars should explore the emotional and psychological aspects of users. I am afraid that the need among individuals to intellectually grow may lose its value as AI is dealing with every single problem. People themselves may fail to notice viable long-term consequences, so we need to constantly monitor the impact of artificial intelligence on individuals.

In my final conclusion, I seriously assert that we have to teach normal people about AI to prevent particular misuse. After taking the necessary precautions, we can ensure Artificial intelligence serves its intended purposes in education and the workplace. The improvement AI has caused by now in Uzbekistan definitely exceeds the few misused cases; This trend encourages the government to switch more sectors to AI-based schemes to gain similar outcomes.

References

1. <https://daryo.uz/en/2024/10/18/uzbekistan-sets-ai-development-strategy-aiming-for-15bn-market-by-2030> (the most prominent and reliable uzbek website for news)
2. Government Portal of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2024). Uzbekistan 2030 Strategy, https://gov.uz/en/pages/2030_strategy
3. Global CIO (2023). Digital transformation of Uzbekistan, <https://globalcio.com/articles/main/digitaltransformation-of-uzbekistan/>.
4. UNICEF (<https://www.unicef.org/uzbekistan/en/stories/supporting-republic-uzbekistan-shaping-future-learning>)
5. International Journal of Studies in Business Management, Economics and Strategies (<https://scholarsdigest.org/index.php/bmes/article/view/611?>)
6. Manuvinakurike et al. (2021) - <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33578736/>
7. Alneyadi, Wardat, Alshannag, & Abu-Al-Aish (2023) - <https://nchr.elsevierpure.com/en/publications/the-role-of-artificial-intelligence-in-education-from-the-perspec?>

8. Walden University, Using AI in learning-
(<https://www.waldenu.edu/programs/education/resource/five-pros-and-cons-of-ai-in-the-education-sector>)
9. Khakimov, F. (2022a). Uzbekistan's Digitalization Policy Achievements and Prospects, Uzbirdge
10. Zarei, Mohammad, Taghizadeh, Mohammad Reza, Moayedi, Seyedeh Samaneh, Naseri, Alireza, Al-Bahrani, Mohammed, & Khordehbinan, Mohammad Worya. (2022). Evaluation of fracture behavior of Warm mix asphalt (WMA) modified with hospital waste pyrolysis carbon black (HWPCB) under freeze–thaw damage (FTD) at low and intermediate temperatures. *Construction and Building Materials*, 356, 129184
11. Khan, Muhammad Farooq, Ahmed, Haron, Almashhadani, Haidar Abdulkareem, Al-Bahrani, Mohammed, Khan, Asif Ullah, Ali, Sharafat, Gul, Nida, Hassan, Tajamul, Ismail, Ahmed, & Zahid, Muhammad. (2022). Sustainable adsorptive removal of high concentration organic contaminants from water using biodegradable Gum-Acacia integrated magnetite nanoparticles hydrogel adsorbent. *Inorganic Chemistry Communications*, 145, 110057.
12. Samad, Abdul. (2022). Antibiotics Resistance in Poultry and its Solution. *Devotion Journal of Community Service*,
13. Al-Bahrani, Mohammed, Majdi, Hasan Shakir, Abed, Azher M., & Cree, Alistair. (2022). An innovated method to monitor the health condition of the thermoelectric cooling system using nanocomposite-based CNTs. *International Journal of Energy Research*, 46(6), 7519–7528.
14. Alneyadi, Saif, Wardat, Yousef, Alshannag, Qasim, & Abu-Al-Aish, Ahmad. (2023). The effect of using smart e-learning app on the academic achievement of eighth-grade students.
15. Tamers, S.L.; Streit, J.; Pana-Cryan, R.; Ray, T.; Syron, L.; Flynn, M.A.; Castillo, D.; Roth, G.; Geraci, C.; Guerin, R.; et al. Envisioning the future of work to safeguard the safety, health, and well-being of the workforce: A perspective from the CDC's National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health. *Am. J. Ind. Med.* 2020, 63, 1065–1084.
16. Parker, L.D. The COVID-19 office in transition: Cost, efficiency and the social responsibility business case. *Account. Audit. Account. J.* 2020, 33, 1943–1967.

17. Green, N.; Tappin, D.; Bentley, T. Working From Home Before, During and After the Covid-19 Pandemic: Implications for Workers and Organisations. *N. Z. J. Employ. Relat.* 2020, 45, 5–16.
18. Manuvinakurike, R.; Velicer, W.F.; Bickmore, T.W. Automated indexing of Internet stories for health behavior change: Weight loss attitude pilot study. *J. Med. Internet Res.* 2014, 16, e285.
19. Wisskirchen, G.; Biacabe, B.T.; Bormann, U.; Muntz, A.; Niehaus, G.; Soler, G.J.; Von Brauchitsch, B. Artificial Intelligence and Robotics and Their Impact on the Workplace; International Bar Association Global Employment Institute: London, UK, 2017.
20. Traum, D.; Swartout, W.; Marsella, S.; Gratch, J. Fight, flight, or negotiate: Believable strategies for conversing under crisis. In *Proceedings of the Lecture Notes in Computer Science (Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*; Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 2005; Volume 3661, pp. 52–64
21. Ernst, E.; Merola, R.; Samaan, D. Economics of artificial intelligence: Implications for the future of work. *IZA J. Labor Policy* 2019, 9.
22. Buchanan, B.G. A (Very) Brief History of Artificial Intelligence. *AI Mag.* 2005, 53. Aryal,